

Rotatory Powers of some Substituted Camphoranilic Acids and Camphorophenyl Imides.

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It has been stated by Rule (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 1127), that groups of like polarity reinforce each other in the *ortho*-position whilst the introduction of a positive and a negative group both of marked polarity leaves the rotation of unsubstituted compounds unaltered. This is supported by the case of the menthyl esters of *o*-disubstituted benzoic acid prepared by Cohen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1892). Singh and Singh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 478) have prepared some disubstituted camphoranilic acids and have determined their rotatory powers in various solvents. They have shown that groups of the same polarity reinforce each other when they are in the *para*-position with respect to one another; for instance 2':5'-dimethylcamphoranilic acid and 5'-nitro-2'-methylcamphoranilic acid exceed any of their respective isomerides in rotatory power. Again groups of opposite polarity neutralise each other's effect when present in *para*-position. The rotatory power of 5'-nitro-2'-methoxycamphoranilic acid is practically the same as that of the unsubstituted compound (*loc. cit.*). The work has been extended to other disubstituted camphoranilic acids and camphoro—disubstituted phenylimides. The following acids and their imides have been prepared: 2':4'- and 3':5'-dimethyl-, 2':4'-dichloro-, 2':5'-methoxy-, 3'-methoxy- and 3'-ethoxycamphoranilic acids. The nitration of 2'- and 3'-methylcamphoranilic acids and 2'-methoxy- and 2'-ethoxycamphoranilic acids has been carried out by the method described in the experimental part. 2'-Methylcamphoranilic acid on nitration gives 4'-nitro-2'-methylcamphoranilic acid as this substance is identical with the condensation product of camphoric anhydride with *m*-nitro-*o*-toluidine, $C_6H_3CH_3 \cdot NH_2 \cdot NO_2$ (1:2:5). The two compounds have practically the same rotatory power (*vide infra* and *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 480). Similarly 2'-methoxycamphoranilic acid on nitration gives 4'-nitro-2'-methoxycamphoranilic acid. Both have feeble rotatory power in all the four solvents

examined (*vide infra* and *loc.cit.*). The following table records the rotatory powers of some camphoranilic acids and the nitro derivatives of a few.

TABLE I.

Substituents.	[M] _D			
	MeOH.	EtOH.	Me ₂ OH.	MeEtCO.
2'-CH ₃ 146	144	98	...
3'-CH ₃ 140	118	89	...
4'-CH ₃ 167	144	120	...
2':4'-Dimethyl	... 163	160.9	117	107
3':5'-Dimethyl	... 135	126	83.6	84
2'-CH ₃ -4'-Nitro	... 92	90	...	74
3'-CH ₃ -2'-Nitro	... -14.9	-25	-26	-17
2'-OCH ₃ 30	28	-16	-10
2'-OCH ₃ -4'-Nitro	...	Feeble rotation in all solvents.		
2'-OC ₂ O ₅ -50	-62	-90	-89
2'-OC ₂ O ₅ -4'-Nitro	... -48	-41.8	-32	-31

A glance at the table will show that the optical rotatory power of 3':5'-dimethylcamphoranilic acid is practically the same as that of the 3'-methylcamphoranilic acid. Again 2':4'-dimethylcamphoranilic acid has practically the same rotation as that of the 4'-methylcamphoranilic acid except in the case of ethyl alcohol where there is a slight increase. The substitution of another CH₃ group in the *meta*-position does not therefore bring about any change.

Nitro group in the 4'-position has a depressing effect upon the rotatory power of the original compound. Thus 2'-methyl-4'-nitro-, 2'-methoxy-4'-nitro-, and 2'-ethoxy-4'-nitro- have all lower values than the original compounds.

The nitro group in the 2'-position in the case of 3'-methyl-2'-nitrocamphoranilic acid lowers the rotation accompanied by a reversal of sign but the effect is not so marked as in the case of 4'-methyl-2'-nitrocamphoranilic acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 480) where the groups are present in the *meta*-position with respect to one another.

Table II records the molecular rotatory powers of 2'-methoxy-, 3'-methoxy-, and 2':5'-methoxycamphoranilic acids.

TABLE II.

Solvent.	$[M]_D$		
	2'-OCH ₃ .	3'-OCH ₃ .	2': 5'-OCH ₃ .
MeOH	30	151.6 (150)	91.7
EtOH	28	127.5 (131)	67.3
Me ₂ CO	-16	99.7 (101)	43.0
MeEtCO	-10	96.7 (-)	44.0

3'-Methoxycamphoranilic acid has the same values of rotatory power as the unsubstituted compound. (The values of the rotatory power of the latter are shown in parentheses in Table II). The OCH₃ group in the 2'-position lowers the values but the effect is not so marked in 2':5'-dimethoxy-, as in the case of the 2'-methoxycamphoranilic acid.

The following table gives the values of 2'-chloro-, 4'-chloro-, and 2':4'-dichlorocamphoranilic acids in four solvents.

TABLE III.

Solvent.	$[M]_D$		
	2'-Chloro.	4'-Chloro.	2':4'-Chloro.
MeOH	57.8	183.0	86.6
EtOH	35.6	158.7	87.4
Me ₂ CO	-40.3	119.0	feeble positive
MeEtCO	-26.6	150.3	do

The chlorine atom in 2'-position has a depressing effect on the rotatory power of the original compound.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Camphoric Anhydride with Substituted Amines.

Camphoric anhydride and the amine (equal mols.) were heated together with fused sodium acetate at 140-45° for 3-4 hours. The product was dissolved in 90 p.c. alcohol, precipitated, extracted with

a dilute solution of alkali to remove any imide, acidified, and crystallised from alcohol. The following acids were prepared:

3':5'-Dimethylcamphoranilic acid crystallised from alcohol in silky needles, m.p. 214-15°. (Found: N, 4.63; Eq. wt., 304. $C_{18}H_{25}O_3N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent. Eq. wt., 303).

The imide is also formed to the extent of about 10 per cent.

2':4'-Dimethylcamphoranilic acid was obtained as a crystalline mass, m.p. 220-21°. (Found: N, 4.64; Eq. wt., 304.7. $C_{18}H_{25}O_3N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent. Eq. wt., 303).

2':4'-Dichlorocamphoranilic acid crystallised from dilute alcohol in white crystals, m.p. 200-01°, yield 30 p.c. (Found: N, 3.2; Eq. wt., 341.5. $C_{16}H_{19}O_3NCl_2$ requires N, 3.15 per cent. Eq. wt., 344). The acid is soluble in the usual organic solvents.

2':5'-Dimethoxycamphoranilic acid crystallised from alcohol in fine needles with a pink tinge, m.p. 137-39°, yield of the acid is almost quantitative. (Found: N, 4.24; Eq. wt., 331. $C_{18}H_{25}O_5N$ requires N, 4.18 per cent. Eq. wt., 335).

3'-Methoxycamphoranilic acid crystallised from 50 p.c. alcohol in white needles, m.p. 186.5°, yield 75 p.c. (approx.). (Found: N, 4.63; Eq. wt., 305.3. $C_{17}H_{23}O_4N$ requires N, 4.57 per cent. Eq. wt., 305).

3'-Ethoxycamphoranilic acid crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m.p. 168°, yield 80 p.c. (approx.). (Found: N, 4.48; Eq. wt., 319. $C_{18}H_{25}O_4N$ requires N, 4.38 per cent. Eq. wt., 319).

Camphoric anhydride could not be condensed with 2:5-dichloroaniline.

Camphoro-2':4'-dichlorophenyl imide crystallised from dilute alcohol to colourless crystals, m.p. 62.5°, yield 20 p.c. (approx.). (Found: N, 4.35. $C_{16}H_{17}ONCl_2$ requires N, 4.29 per cent.).

Camphoro-2':5'-dimethoxyphenyl imide crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless crystals, m.p. 111-12°, yield 75 p.c. (approx.) (acid, m.p. 137-39°). (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{18}H_{23}O_4N$ requires N, 4.41 per cent.).

Camphoro-m-methoxyphenyl imide crystallised from alcohol in colourless crystals, m.p. 121-23°, yield 75 p.c. (approx.). (Found: N, 5.0. $C_{17}H_{21}O_3N$ requires N, 4.88 per cent.).

Camphoro-m-ethoxyphenyl imide crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless crystalline mass, m.p. 93-95°. The yield is comparatively less in this case, 50 p.c. (Found: N, 4.89. $C_{18}H_{25}O_3N$ requires N, 4.65 per cent.).

Camphoro-2':6'-dimethylphenyl imide crystallised from dilute alcohol in a crystalline colourless product, m.p. 154-55°. (acid, m.p. 236-38°), yield 80 p.c. (approx.). (Found: N, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{23}O_2N$ requires N, 4.91 per cent.).

Nitration of Camphoranilic Acids.

To a mixture of fuming nitric acid (10 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (8 c.c.) 3 g. of the compound were gradually added. The clear solution obtained after 5-10 minutes was kept $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then poured on crushed ice. The precipitate obtained was crystallised from alcohol.

2'-Methoxy-4'-nitrocamphoranilic acid.—The reaction mixture was added drop by drop into ice-cold water, otherwise a large amount of resinous matter was obtained. Crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow crystals, m.p. 182-84°. (Found: N, 8.28. $C_{17}H_{22}O_6N_2$ requires N, 8.0 per cent.).

This compound is identical with the condensation product of camphoric anhydride with *m*-nitro-*o*-anisidine $C_6H_3 \cdot OCH_3 \cdot NH_2 \cdot NO_2$ (1:2:5) prepared by Singh and Singh (*loc. cit.*). They give the melting point 185-86°. Both have feeble rotations, the former having $[\alpha]_D$, 5.7 and the latter $[\alpha]_D$, 5.0 in methylethyl ketone.

2'-Ethoxy-4'-nitrocamphoric acid.—This was similarly poured into cold water and crystallised in yellow coloured bars from dilute alcohol, m.p. 171-73°. (Found: N, 8.0. $C_{18}H_{24}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.7 per cent.).

2'-Methyl-4'-nitrocamphoranilic acid.—The reaction mixture on being poured into ice, separated as a resinous matter which on crystallisation from dilute alcohol gave brownish yellow needles, m.p. 226-28°. (Found: N, 8.5. $C_{17}H_{22}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.38 per cent.).

The nitration product of 2'-methylcamphoranilic acid is identical with 2'-methyl-4'-nitrocamphoranilic acid obtained by Singh and Singh by condensing camphoric anhydride with *m*-nitro-*o*-toluidine (*loc. cit.*). They give the m.p. 229-30°, and the following values for rotatory powers $[\alpha]_D$, in methyl alcohol, 29.1°; ethyl alcohol, 24°; and methylethyl ketone, 23°. The values of the substance prepared by the authors for the same solvents are 27.6°, 27° and 22.4°.

3'-Methyl-2' (or 6')-nitrocamphoranilic acid.—The reaction product was poured into ice. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow

crystals, m.p. 139-40°. (Found: N, 8.4. $C_{17}H_{22}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.38 per cent.).

Rotatory Powers of Mono- and Disubstituted Camphoranilic Acids and Imides.

TABLE IV.

Solvent.	2' : 4'-Dimethylcamphor- anilic acid.		3' : 5'-Dimethylcamphor- anilic acid.		2'-Methyl-4'-nitro- camphoranilic acid.	
	Conc. g/25c.c.	[M] _D	Conc. g/25c.c.	[M] _D	Conc. g/25c.c.	[M] _D
MeOH	0.1780	163°	0.2034	135.7°	0.1178	92.0°
EtOH	0.1813	160.9	0.2248	126.3	0.1482	90.1
Me ₂ CO	0.1734	117.5	0.1989	83.6	—	—
MeEtCO	0.2196	107.0	0.1574	84.2	0.1784	74.8
	3'-Methyl 6'-nitro- camphoranilic acid.		2'-Methoxy-4'-nitro- camphoranilic acid.		2'-Ethoxy-4'-nitro- camphoranilic acid.	
MeOH	0.1870	-14.09			0.2533	-48.48
EtOH	0.1492	-25.18	Shows feeble rotatory power in all the solvents.		0.3261	-41.86
Me ₂ CO	0.1920	-26.12			0.4125	-31.99
MeEtCO	0.1858	-17.26			0.3672	-30.97
	2' : 5'-Dimethoxy- camphoranilic acid.		2' : 4'-Dichloro- camphoranilic acid.		3'-Methoxy- camphoranilic acid.	
MeOH	0.3215	91.74	0.1932	86.6	0.2675	151.6
EtOH	0.3488	67.3	0.1572	87.4	0.2238	127.5
Me ₂ CO	0.3015	43.0	Feeble rotations.		0.2291	99.7
MeEtCO	0.2180	44.0			0.2160	99.7
	3'-Ethoxycamphor- anilic acid.		Camphoro-2' : 5'-dimethoxy- phenyl imide.		Camphoro-3'-methoxy- phenyl imide.	
MeOH	0.2096	159.5	0.2040	34.9	0.2806	38.75
EtOH	0.2205	147.0	0.2136	29.5	0.1937	42.48
Me ₂ CO	0.2055	104.7	—	—	0.2156	39.90
MeEtCO	0.2487	109.0	—	—	0.2198	37.55

TABLE IV. (*Contd.*)

Solvent.	Camphoro-3'-ethoxy- phenyl imide.		Camphoro-2' : 6'-dimethyl- phenyl imide	
MeOH	0.2040	62.6	0.2137	46.8
EtOH	0.2126	58.3	0.2175	45.8
Me ₂ CO	0.1912	43.1	0.2152	37.9
MeEtCO	0.1550	38.84	0.2184	39.0

The readings were taken in a 2 dm. tube within half hour of making up the solution. There was no mutarotation. Temperature of the room was 19-20°.

Summary.

A number of new monosubstituted and disubstituted camphoranilic acids have been prepared and their rotatory powers determined. It has been shown that a second CH₃ group in the *meta*-position does not alter the rotation of the original compound. Further nitro group in the 4'-position has a depressing effect on the rotatory power. Thus 2'-methyl-4'-nitrocamphoranilic acid, 2'-methoxy-4'-nitrocamphoranilic acid and 2'-ethoxy-4'-nitrocamphoranilic acid have lower rotatory power than the original compound.

Methoxy and chloro groups in the 2'-position have also depressing influence, as shown by the rotatory powers of 2' : 5'-dimethoxy- and 2' : 4'-dichlorocamphoranilic acids.

